

Interview Guide for On-boarding case study

Interview questions for developers

Background

1. Can you describe a little bit about yourself (role, team, experience etc.)?
2. Can you tell us a little bit about your team (team health check, competence matrix)?
3. Do you have previous working experience before joining the team?
4. Have you worked with agile before joining the team?
5. What kind of tools or programming languages do you use in your team?

On-Boarding

6. Describe your on-boarding experience (activities, people involved etc.).
7. How long was the on-boarding process?
8. What were the challenges during the on-boarding process?
9. How did the team transfer technical knowledge to you?
10. We would like you to rate a list of on-boarding activities and explain why.
11. Which activities are most helpful for technical knowledge transfer?
12. What kind of agile activities do you think are helpful for on-boarding newcomers
13. Is there anything you think could be improved about the on-boarding process

Open question

13. Do you have anything else that you would like to share?

Interview questions for Managers

Background

1. Can you describe a little bit about yourself (role, team, experience etc.)?
2. Can you tell us a little bit about your team (team health check, competence matrix)?

On-Boarding

3. Describe your on-boarding experience (activities, people involved etc.).
4. Have you onboarded any new team members to your team? How many?
5. Does your team have an on-boarding plan, for example a roadmap (guideline)?
6. What is your responsibility during the on-boarding of a new team member?
7. What kind of on-boarding activities do you have when a new people join the team?
8. How long is the on-boarding process?
9. What are the challenges for new team members joining your team?
10. How does your team do knowledge transfer to newcomers?
11. We would like you to rate a list of on-boarding activities and explain why.
12. Which activities are most helpful for technical knowledge transfer?
13. Which activities are most helpful for understand agile?
14. Is there anything you think could be improved about the on-boarding process?

Open question

14. Do you have anything else that you would like to share?